

When Divorce Becomes A Moral Trial: Fault, Gender, and Lived Experiences Under Ghana's Matrimonial Causes Act, 1971 (Act 367)

*Elijah Tukwariba Yin
Peter Atudiwe Atupare*

Abstract: Irretrievable breakdown of marriage remains the sole legal ground for dissolution of marriage in Ghana; however, this ground is established through fault-based facts, as stipulated under Section 2 of Act 367. This study examines the structure of the Act as fault-based and assesses its practicality in light of modern-day social realities. Using the lenses of sociological jurisprudence, feminist legal theory, doctrinal analysis, and conversational interview data from divorcees, family lawyers, and legal academics, it is argued that Act 367 is anchored in a fault-based framework that is inconsistent with contemporary social realities. The findings reveal that fault remains the fulcrum around which the Act functions. To the extent that spouses who jointly agree to dissolve their marriage peacefully and quickly are still required to prove the breakdown of their marriage through allegations of misconduct. It was also found that the two separation grounds defined by the Act remain largely remote, and the divorce process itself brings about psycho-emotional and social burdens. The study concludes that the fault-based grounds specified by Act 367 do not align with contemporary social realities, expectations of dignity, women's autonomy, and fairness.

Key words: Divorce, Marriage, Fault-based, Social realities, Power imbalance

INTRODUCTION

The Matrimonial Causes Act (MCA), 1971 (Act 367) is the statutory regime that regulates divorce and its associated matrimonial reliefs in Ghana (Atupare & Yin, 2024; Akoto, 2024; Atta-Boahene, 2010). Before the Act came into force, marriage and divorce were generally governed by customary practices of local traditional areas and English matrimonial law principles established by the colonial regime (Akoto, 2024; Teye, 2022). The Act aimed to regulate, shape, and harmonize the law of

divorce in post-independence Ghana. The concept of irretrievable breakdown of marriage was introduced by the Act as the sole and fundamental basis of divorce (Atupare & Yin, 2024). Based on factual situations, the Act defines irretrievable breakdown to reflect some traditional fault categories such as adultery (section 2(1)(a)), unreasonable behaviour (section 2(1)(b)), and desertion for a minimum duration of two consecutive years immediately preceding the submission of the petition (section 2(1)(c)). The Act also mentions separation with consent for two (2) years (Section 2(1)(d)), and living apart for a specified period of at least five years preceding the presentation of the petition (Section 2(1)(e)) as bases for divorce. The language of Act 367 appears neutral; however, its practical application involves proving misconduct by one party. To understand the current structure of Act 367, it is important to trace the historical influences that shaped its development.

The Matrimonial Causes Act of 1857, 1923, and 1937 in England and Wales influenced the MCA 1971 (Act 367) of Ghana. The historical roots and character of the latter reveal it as a kind of legal transplant. After Ghana attained independence in 1957, the country inherited the English matrimonial legal system, coupled with the customary laws of local communities (Skinner, 2020; Hammond, 2016; Akpaloo, 1994; Asante, 1964; Ollennu, 1971). Each legal regime, whether the inherited formal matrimonial legal system or customary legal system, functioned at a different level of the social structure. This created a form of legal pluralism within the marriage and divorce space (Akoto, 2024; Chala & Gemedede, 2022; Hern, 2022; Tweneboah, 2019; Hammond, 2016). This pluralism governed the system of marriage and divorce, but with different requirements and expectations. These historical influences raise questions about whether Act 367 reflects Ghana's own social norms and expectations surrounding marriage and divorce.

Some scholars argue that after Ghana gained independence from the British, the legal regime of marriage and divorce should have been developed along the lines of Ghanaian traditional marriage practices (Crawford, 1971). This means that in formulating Act 367, the then legislature failed to question and include the conceptions of marriage, divorce, family, and dispute resolution strategies of local communities. The legislature reproduced a marriage regime where misconduct and the burden of blame remain a central feature of marital dissolution. This prevailing legal regime, through the courts, continues to shape how people think and express marriage and divorce in contemporary Ghana. Given the expressive nature of marriage, a closer look at how the principle of irretrievable breakdown actually functions within the current legal framework is necessary.

As already stated, irretrievable breakdown of marriage remains the sole legal ground of marriage dissolution in Ghana (Atupare & Yin, 2024), yet this ground is proved through fault-based facts, as stipulated under section 2 of the Act. Apart from separation for two years with consent and five years without consent, the rest of the grounds require some proof of wrongdoing (Parkman, 2019; Osuagwu et al., 2023). The literature from the divorce courts suggests that most spouses rely on allegations of adultery, unreasonable behaviour, and desertion. To prove these forms of allegations requires the alleging party to show evidence of intimacy and call a witness(s) to establish the existence of misconduct in the marriage. This makes non-fault grounds for divorce generally not accessible to those who wish to initiate divorce due to power imbalances and economic dependence. The Act, instead of promoting cooperative dissolution of marriage, encourages adversarial accusations (Amara, 2024; Weitzman, 1985; Mnookin & Kornhauser, 1979). To the extent that courts look out for personal misconduct to arrive at a decision. It appears that, rather than the legal termination of a relationship that has failed, the divorce process has become more of a moral and character trial. This means that although the legal language seems neutral, the reality of its operation remains fault-driven. These observations lead naturally to the question of how the judiciary applies these provisions in real cases.

The jurisprudence of the Ghanaian courts regarding Act 367 presents the regime as one grounded in the principle of irretrievable breakdown of marriage; however, the requirements of proof of the facts are mostly fault-driven. In cases like *Yeboah v. Yeboah*, *Mensah v. Mensah*, *Arthur v. Arthur*, and *Quartson v. Quartson*, the courts re-established that the petitioner for divorce had the burden to prove any of the grounds stated in section 2 of Act 367. It also emerged that even when the court adopted a liberal approach to evidence, the responsibility for attributing marital failure remained. From the available judicial decisions, it can be said that Ghana's marital legal regime, in both form and substance, remains accusatorial and more of a moral trial than a legal one. It is worth noting that this fault-based approach, whether explicitly or implicitly, has implications for who maintains and takes custody of the children and property distribution (Atupare & Yin, 2025). The bases for divorce under the Act and the litigation process are often characterised by protracted conflicts, pent-up emotional resentments, and stigmatization. One cannot blame the courts for their fault-laden approach, since they are required to function within the remits of the Act. This judicial trend reinforces the broader social impact of fault-based litigation, which extends beyond the courtroom.

Beyond the scope of the Act, the fault-based orientation is further entrenched by the Ghanaian socio-cultural realities. Marriage is touted

as an enduring cultural and moral institution in Ghana, with a high premium placed on it. Divorce is not regarded or seen to be the outcome of a neutral legal consequence, but the failure of parties to maintain their union, which is expected to last till death. This cultural orientation and expectation tend to interact well with Act 367. It is this interaction that promotes stigmatization and further discourages non-fault-based exits from marriage. The practice of discussing private marital life, including proving the character flaws and moral ineptitudes of a partner in open court, prevents partners who are vulnerable from seeking legal relief. In Ghana, women, particularly, face these disproportionate risks. The evidentiary fault-proof, coupled with the socio-cultural realities, has trapped many women in marriages that can be described as dysfunctional. This has also resulted in many women being involved in an informal separation without any legal remedy or protection. The current structure of the law, to a large extent, does not effectively and efficiently serve its protective functions. It compounds harm rather than offers a peaceful and dignified exit. This interplay between law and culture raises important questions about the Act's continued relevance and effectiveness.

The realities of the issues raised call for serious academic engagement with the Act to establish its current viability in Ghanaian society. The available literature on family law has generally paid attention to the causes of divorce (Atupare & Yin, 2024), child custody (Atupare & Yin, 2025), maintenance (Cudjoe et al., 2025), and the distribution of property under the Act (Sam, 2012; Dowuona-Hammond, 2005). The fault-based foundation of the Act has received limited critique (Fenrich, 2015; Dowuona-Hammond, 2019). The presence of irretrievable breakdown has been acknowledged by some scholars (Atupare & Yin, 2024); however, very few scholars have examined the tension between the fault-based statutory proof and the concept of irretrievable breakdown and courtroom divorce practice. The literature available shows that studies on how the experiences of divorce litigants are impacted by the fault-based approach to divorce and how this approach affects access to justice are limited in Ghana and other common law jurisdictions in Africa. This lacuna leaves many questions unanswered. Additionally, whether the Act resonates with the socio-cultural realities of contemporary marriage and divorce also raises questions. This study, therefore, through a doctrinal and empirical approach, aims to examine the fault-based foundations of Act 367. It is argued that the operative provisions of Act 367 continue to require proof of misconduct in a matrimonial union, irrespective of the courts' references to the irretrievable breakdown of marriage. It is further contended that the proof of fault or misconduct that underpins the Act is not consistent with

the current social realities associated with marriage and divorce in Ghana, hence, requiring a legislative shift.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORKS

This study used sociological jurisprudence and feminist legal theory to advance its analysis. The former, advanced by Roscoe Pound, is a theoretical perspective that focuses on law and its relation to society (Gardner, 1961; 1912; Yin & Atupare, 2024). This perspective examines the impact of the law on society and how social conditions tend to influence the framing of the law (Hahn, 2022; Catanzariti, 2024; Hydén, 2014). The works of Tamanaha (2020), Cotterell (2017), and Mamonto, Putri, & Salsabila (2025) posit the sociological school of jurisprudence as a communal tool that engages the dynamic nature of social conditions rather than stagnant moral principles. It concerns itself with the actual role of law in meeting social needs and the lived experiences of people in society (Pound, 1912; Tamanaha, 2020; Cotterell, 2017; Mamonto, Putri, & Salsabila, 2025).

This theoretical perspective reveals the divide between social realities and the grounds for divorce set by the court or statute. Studies have shown that most marriages collapse due to infertility (Takyi, 2002), economic or financial hardship (Atupare & Yin, 2024; Mbwambo, 2020), lack of affection (Oppong, Osafo, & Nyamekye, 2014), mental health challenges (Hoge, 2016), lack of communication and differences in personality (Uygarer, Uzunboylu & Kagan, 2015), long-distance relationships (Muwana, 2022), substance abuse (Hoge, 2016), and irreconcilable differences in life goals (Brake, 2012), and not necessarily because of moral wrongdoing. Reinforcing these research outcomes is the recent scholarly work of Atupare and Yin (2024). They found that the bases for divorce in Ghana are not necessarily legal but social. They revealed that, while Act 367 sets out the grounds for divorce in section 2, most participants in their study did not consider those grounds their actual basis for divorce. This means that the law is out of touch with the social realities of happenings in marriages in Ghana. Yet, spouses seeking divorce are expected to frame their basis along the fault-based lines defined in the Act. From this theoretical standpoint, these fault-based grounds, which are not in sync with current social realities, undermine the social utility of family law, which is expected to promote the stability of society, fairness, and the peaceful exit from collapsed marriages. The application of this theory is a call for the reformation of Ghana's Matrimonial Causes Act, driven by people's lived experiences, changing socio-cultural norms, and the socially responsive nature of law.

Feminist legal theory, on the other hand, pays attention to how the law reproduces and entrenches gender inequality and patriarchal power relations (Thomas, 2021; Painter, 2015). This perspective explains how women and men are affected differently by legal rules in society (Painter, 2015). In applying this theory to the Act, it reveals that the fault-based grounds put an unequal burden on men and women during divorce. This disadvantages women, although on the face of the statute, its legal framing appears neutral. Generally, in Ghana, women are dependent economically, constrained socially, and disadvantaged in their attempt to access evidence (Bazaanah & Ngcobo, 2024). Women are also structurally disadvantaged in terms of requiring proof of adultery, desertion, and cruelty because such moral violations take place within the private space, where evidence is difficult to obtain (Dowuona-Hammond, Atuguba & Tuokuu, 2020). The process of women seeking a divorce can be traumatizing, especially for those suffering from emotional and psychological abuse and domestic violence (Fischel-Wolovick, 2018; Latifah & Peristiano, 2024). Culturally, women are also disadvantaged in airing their views on sexual and marital issues (Apatinga, 2019; Adjei, 2017). Given the gender double standard in sexual attitudes, women suffer heavily when accused of sexual misconduct. This cultural position weakens the reputation of women and their ability to meet the evidentiary standards set by the law. Unlike women, men suffer less reputation risk from allegations of adultery, desertion, or unreasonable behaviour. This theory exposes the embeddedness of the unequal power relations in the current legal regime under the pretext of fostering moral accountability. In effect, this theory calls for a legal regime that recognises and supports the dignity, integrity, and autonomy of women.

The combined use of these theories explains the contemporary social realities of marriage, divorce, and the gendered power dynamics.

METHODS

The research philosophy guiding this study is interpretivism. This philosophy shares that law and people's experiences are well understood through the meaning people give to them based on how they apply, experience, and critique them. From the interpretivist perspective, law is not an abstract set of rules or rules practiced in abstraction, but rather a social institution that is shaped by human experiences. This philosophical understanding informs the qualitative approach to research.

Anchored in this interpretivist outlook, the study relied on qualitative interviews to capture the lived experiences and interpretations of divorce litigants and practitioners. This approach aims to provide first-hand information and deeper insight into real-world problems affecting society. It involves gathering and analyzing contextualized experiential data to understand pre-existing and emerging socio-legal issues. This approach was adopted to examine people's experiences with Ghana's Matrimonial Causes Act, 1971 (Act 367). The rationale for this approach is to understand people's opinions, experiences, and the practical realities about the Act. The study also adopted a doctrinal-empirical research design. This design allows researchers to combine legal texts and empirical insights to determine the applicability of law to social realities.

As part of the doctrinal component, the study undertook a close analysis of the Matrimonial Causes Act, 1971 (Act 367) and relevant judicial decisions. This entailed examining the internal structure of sections 1 and 2 of the Act, how the statutory grounds for divorce are framed, and how courts have applied them in cases such as *Yeboah v Yeboah*, *Mensah v Mensah*, *Arthur v Arthur*, and *Quartson v Quartson*. The analysis clarified the evidentiary burdens placed on spouses and demonstrated that, although the Act appears neutral, its operation remains fault-based in practice. This doctrinal review provided a legal foundation for interpreting the empirical data and assessing the consistency between written law and lived experience.

Aside from Act 367, which was readily available for analysis, the study used an in-depth interview guide. The guide was composed of only open-ended questions. The questions focused on gathering data from divorcees, family lawyers, and legal academics. Insights from the doctrinal analysis informed the structure of the interview guide by highlighting the areas where participants' lived experiences were needed to clarify how the Act operates in practice. The guide was structured based on the following themes: The experiences of proving misconduct in divorce trials, people's perceptions of the fairness of Act 367, problems posed by fault-based litigation, and views on the no-fault divorce system in Ghana. The use of an interview guide with open-ended questions permitted participants to freely express their views on the subject matter in any way they wanted. The use of open-ended questions allowed some flexibility to probe further during the interviews.

This study used the purposive sampling technique to identify and select information-rich cases related to the phenomenon of interest. This technique was used because it focuses on participants who have knowledge and experience about the matter under study and can offer

direct information to address the research objective. The unit of analysis for this study comprised divorcees, family lawyers, and legal academics. These categories of people were selected based on the kind of information they have to inform the study. The rationale for interviewing divorcees was based on their experience with the divorce process under the Act. Family lawyers were interviewed because of their daily engagement with marriage and divorce processes and their experiences with the application of the Act in court. Legal practitioners were selected due to their practical engagement with matrimonial litigation and their familiarity with courtroom application of the Act. The legal academics were interviewed because of their capacity to offer theoretical perspectives on the matrimonial regime of Ghana. In all, 57 participants were interviewed, comprising 32 divorcees (19 females and 13 males), 14 family lawyers (6 females and 8 males), and 11 legal academics (2 females and 9 males). This sample was useful as the study did not aim to claim generalizability but rather offer an in-depth understanding of the issues under study. The principle of saturation was applied to the categories of participants. According to Straus and Cobin (1998) and Hennink and Kaiser (2022), data saturation is reached when new cases no longer reveal new features. In effect, after interviewing 28 divorcees, 11 family lawyers, and 7 legal academics, the additional participants who were interviewed offered no new information. It was therefore concluded that data saturation was reached. The interviews were both manually and digitally recorded.

To ensure the trustworthiness and credibility of the data, the data gathered from divorcees, family lawyers, and legal academics were triangulated to compare perspectives. After transcribing and typing out the data, the transcript was shared with selected participants to confirm whether the information captured actually represented their views. Given the normative nature of the subject under study, to minimise bias, reflexivity was maintained throughout the research process. Collectively, the findings of this study were enhanced by these measures.

The collected data were analyzed according to these five procedures. Initially, subsequent to the interviews, the assorted notes obtained from the participants were consolidated and transcribed into a single Word document. The recorded interviews were transcribed and typed. Secondly, the typed information was printed for convenient study and examination. This enabled the researcher to read the data multiple times for comprehension. At this level, observations were recorded regarding concepts and reflections. In the third stage, preliminary codes were established. Keywords and phrases were noted and inscribed at the margins of the printed document. After this phase, the codes were studied and organized into themes. The identified themes were the

persistence of fault in divorce practices, the adversarial strain and emotional toll, the gendered implications of fault-based divorce, practical obstacles to obtaining non-fault separation grounds, and advocacy for a no-fault divorce system. These themes were mapped onto the research questions to maintain coherence between the aims of the study and the issues emerging from the data. The themes were systematically organized and presented logically to narrate individuals' thoughts and experiences under Act 367.

The doctrinal and qualitative components were integrated. While the doctrinal analysis established the formal legal expectations and procedural logic of Act 367, the interviews revealed how those rules are experienced by divorcees, lawyers, and legal academics. This integration allowed the study to compare legal text with courtroom reality and provided a fuller socio-legal understanding of the divorce process under Ghana's matrimonial regime.

This study complied with the ethical principles of social and legal research. Before data collection, a consent form was created, and participants were requested to review and sign it. The researcher elucidated the participants' rights to withdraw from the study at any point. Individuals were also informed of their right to decline to respond to unsettling questions. Participants were adequately notified that the interviews would be recorded both manually and digitally. The participants were guaranteed anonymity and confidentiality. Their actual names would not be utilized in the primary work. Participants were categorized using tags such as divorcee 1, family lawyer 1, legal academic 1, among others. This means that their responses were disassociated from their real identities (Hoft, 2021; Novak, 2014). In respect of confidentiality, information such as the location of divorcees, court firms of family lawyers, the institutional affiliation of legal academics, and names of participants were coded and encrypted on the computer to prevent access by any other person (Hoft, 2021). The handwritten transcripts have also been securely kept. These ethical issues were considered to minimize risks and harms and maximize benefits; privacy, respect for human dignity, and autonomy (Resnik, 2015; Novak, 2014). The results are presented below.

RESULTS

Doctrinal Analysis of Ghana's Matrimonial Causes Act, 1971 (Act 367)

Section 1 of Act 367 identifies the only legal basis for divorce in Ghana as the marriage being broken down irretrievably. This may sound nice on the face of the law, as it tends to suggest a protective and sustainable matrimonial legal framework or a move from a fault-based approach to a no-fault-based approach. However, the “spirit” underpinning it requires proof of fault before a marriage can be dissolved. This means that the court cannot just dissolve a marriage on the assumption or finding of its collapse, as section 2 requires proof of the marriage breakdown based on facts such as adultery, desertion, unreasonable behaviour, etc. These are mandatory prerequisites that need to be proven before any relief can be granted by the court, as the court has no discretion outside of these legal categories to dissolve any marriage. What this implies is that the irretrievable breakdown does not prove itself but rather a quasi-fault fact or fault-based fact that is legally constructed. This position requires interrogation, as it is the defining characteristic that distinguishes it from a no-fault-based approach of dissolving marriage.

According to section 2(1) of Act 367, an irretrievable breakdown of marriage must be proven based on any of the following: adultery, unreasonable behaviour, desertion, separation for two years with consent, and separation for five years without consent. A cursory understanding of these facts, as the requirement of proof, reveals at least three classical fault grounds. For example, an allegation of adultery, which is a sexual misconduct, is expected to be proven by the alleged party. The party alleging unreasonable behaviour must prove that the respondent's behaviour makes it impossible for him or her to live with them. For desertion, the petitioner must show evidence of deliberate abandonment by the respondent. On all these grounds, the petitioners are expected to show evidence of misconduct against the respondents. The position of the law puts fault at the centre stage of the divorce process. The other grounds, that is, separation for two years with consent and five years without consent, which look like a no-fault-based are designed with no genuine options. For instance, in the situation of separation for two years, consent is expected from the respondent. As a form of control over the divorce process, this consent can be withheld. The separation for five years without consent practically puts a long-term psychological burden on the parties. Given the current form of the matrimonial legal framework, proving misconduct or fault is the only

means of getting a divorce granted, despite the Act's central position of irretrievable breakdown.

It is obvious that, under the Act, the petitioner has the burden of proof based on the legally defined elements, on the balance of probabilities. The petitioner, bearing the burden and its associated legal test, supports the structure of the legal system. The courts would expect proof of inclination and opportunity in the case of adultery. In a case of unreasonable behaviour, the party alleging is expected to lead evidence of misconduct that meets the doctrinal test of an objective standard of unreasonableness. In desertion cases, the lack of consent and the intention to desert must be established, with proof of physical separation between the parties. This matrimonial legal regime is inherently adversarial, as it is more of an evidentiary fault-fact contest and blame game. It can logically be deduced that the respondent, whose behaviour is judicially evaluated, is viewed by society as a person who has failed morally. This position of fault-based divorce is not consistent with the aspirations of a modern society. The law, as it is framed, focuses on moral judgment rather than avoiding it. It appears that the law rather entices individuals into egregious misconduct just to be granted a divorce. The Matrimonial Act needs a fresh breath that will place its aim on the factual reality of marital breakdown.

The Ghanaian courts have not departed from the fault-based structure of the Act. In *Yeboah v. Yeboah*, *Mensah v. Mensah*, *Arthur v. Arthur*, and *Quartson v. Quartson*, *Antwi v. Antwi*, *Adjetey and Another v. Adjetey*, *Patricia Abena v. Verdoes Koranchie*, and *Oppong v. Oppong*, the court depended on section 2 requirements to dissolve the marriages. For instance, in *Adjetey v. Adjetey*, the court found that the petitioner had committed adultery and deserted the matrimonial home, and that the marriage had broken down beyond reconciliation under section 2(3) of the Matrimonial Causes Act, 1971. Also, in *Antwi v. Antwi*, the Petitioner alleged physical abuse, abandonment, and adultery by the Respondent. They have resided separately for more than a decade. The respondent denied some of the allegations but agreed that the marriage should be dissolved. The court examined whether the marriage had irretrievably broken down, as mandated by the Act. The judge regarded the petitioner's testimony as credible and duly accepted her evidence regarding the dissolution of the marriage. Based on the fact that the parties have lived apart for more than ten years, the court reasoned that the marriage was irretrievably broken down. The court satisfied itself that the years of apartness were beyond the five-year period the Act stipulates. The court, therefore, dissolved the marriage. In cases of alleged adultery and desertion, the courts have generally insisted on credible and corroborated evidence. It is as though the court is saying to

the would-be divorcees that the most rapid and expedient way to get a divorce is to engage in outrageous conduct or a heinous act, and/or be ready to impugn the integrity of the other party. Despite emphasising irretrievable breakdown, the courts' reasoning is anchored on proving fault. This shows how the practice of the judiciary has further ingrained the misconduct-based logic rather than diluting it.

Under the Act, the influence of fault goes beyond the marriage dissolution into determining other reliefs. Despite the court indicating that custody, maintenance, and distribution of property must not be characterised as punishment in nature, marital misconducts have the propensity to influence judicial outcomes. In that, an adulterous spouse stands disadvantage to the other when it comes to determining custody of children. Explicitly or implicitly, this makes the process of divorce and its outcomes a punishment rather than a reorganization of family relations through a neutral legal arena. This doctrinal analysis shows that moving towards a no-fault regime extends beyond courts into the amendment role of the legislature.

EMPIRICAL FINDINGS

This section presents the empirical findings of the study under the following themes: persistence of fault in divorce practices, the adversarial strain and emotional toll, the gendered implications of fault-based divorce, practical obstacles to obtaining non-fault separation grounds, and advocacy for a no-fault divorce system.

Under the persistence of fault in divorce practice, participants shared their own experiences. According to a family lawyer with 15 years of legal practice experience:

In divorce cases in Ghana, the alleged partner, whether the wife or husband, has to prove that the other partner misconducted him or herself against the marriage. As a lawyer of 15 years at the Bar, I can say without a doubt that the divorce cases we handle in court are built around fault. The cases will not proceed without any fault base. (Family Lawyer, 3, Age: 52)

Another family lawyer indicated the importance of building a divorce case around fault in daily practice:

Simply saying that the marriage is irretrievably broken down in court is not enough. The sitting judge is likely to ask you the grounds upon which such an argument is being made. You either have to argue adultery, unreasonable

behaviour, or desertion, or any of the other grounds stated in the law. (Family Lawyer, 5, Age: 47)

In recounting her experience in court as a lawyer, family lawyer 6 said:

I am handling a divorce case where both parties have agreed to divorce. When we got to court, the judge insisted on knowing the grounds for divorce as stipulated in Act 367. When the judge asked the parties directly, all they said was that they were no longer interested in each other. The judge told them that the court cannot dissolve their marriage just because they are not interested in each other. The judge asked them to go and think through and come back with proper reasons grounded in the law. What do you think will happen? The parties will begin to think of coming up with faults against each other. They will begin to call past unpleasant events. This is why I strongly believe that our law on divorce is fault-driven. (Family Lawyer, 6, Age: 55)

The divorcees who were interviewed corroborated what family lawyers 3, 5, and 6 said. According to them, they were forced to allege misconduct against each other even in situations where a peaceful dissolution was required. Divorcee 7, male participant, said that:

My ex-wife and I had agreed that the marriage was not working and that we should call it off. But the lawyer I hired told me that was not enough for the court to grant me a divorce. The lawyer said that based on what I have discussed with him, I should accuse my wife of unreasonable behaviour. And that, it is only upon an accusation against my wife that the court will proceed to act. (Divorcee 7, Age: 46)

Divorcee 3, female participant, shared a similar experience:

My husband was engaged in an adulterous life. Even so, it was my wish to leave the marriage quietly because I had children with him. But given the divorce process, I had no option but to accuse him of adultery. The adultery accusation was not a major concern. I was just fed up with the marriage and wanted to leave. (Divorcee 3, Age: 49)

According to some participants, irrespective of the main reason for the marital breakdown, they had to forge stories to match the legal requirements. In the words of divorcee 1, female participant:

We wanted to divorce. It was a consensus, but knowing that the court would not listen to us, we had to forge stories to enrich our grounds. We didn't tell the court the actual story of why the marriage had collapsed. We gave them what they wanted to hear. My former husband and I are still cool. (Divorcee 1, Age: 40)

Another divorcee added, female participant 14:

The marriage was over. It didn't take a day. It died over time, but slowly. And yet the court wanted me to submit acts of wrongdoing against the man. It was really a surprise to me that I could not just divorce by signing the divorce papers, but blame someone. When the lawyer told me the basis upon which the court can grant me a divorce, I was shocked. In this day and age. The law is a problem. (Divorcee 14, Age: 38)

This position was confirmed by two legal academics who were interviewed. It was confirmed by them that, theoretically and practically, proving fault was the main engine of facilitating divorce litigation. Legal academic 4, male participant observed:

The language of the Act concerns itself with irretrievable breakdown. Yet to prove this irretrievable breakdown is about proving fault. That is how the Act is structured. Even based on case law, the court has not abandoned proving fault. (Legal academic 4, Age: 45)

The second legal academic, male participant 2, pointed out how the statutory language differs from courtroom reality:

What is captured in the Act as an irretrievable breakdown is just in name. The reality of what happens in our court is different from theory. The Act is operational based on alleging and proving wrong. Without that, the irretrievable breakdown means nothing. (Legal academic 2, Age: 48)

It can be understood from the narratives above that proving fault is the functional operating feature of Ghana's Matrimonial Act. Even in situations where parties mutually agree to divorce, they are forced to tell untrue stories to meet the legal requirements.

Apart from describing the persistence fault-based of the Act by participants, it was also described as adversarial or as content with its consequential emotional burden. The divorce process was described as a

contest between the spouses over moral issues, character, and credibility. According to family lawyer 2, a male participant:

From my experience as a lawyer, I have realised that whenever a party pleads adultery or unreasonable behaviour, specifically, cruelty, the issue moves from ending the marriage to insulting and tarnishing the credibility of the other person. (Family lawyer 2, Age: 36)

Family lawyer 9 expressed how the divorce process ends up being transformed from a private family issue into public evidence:

You know, these divorce cases are sometimes heard in open court. And these parties are compelled to share what they once considered private, that is, the details of their sexual lives in open court. In an attempt to prove the fault of another, all private intimate issues become part of public. (Family lawyer 9, Age: 41)

Two divorcees explained that the whole divorce process was humiliating and emotionally challenging: A male divorcee, participant 14, said:

In fact, one of the most humiliating and degrading parts of my life was when I appeared in court to testify about my ex-wife's adulterous behaviour. It actually made me feel very little in the eyes of all those who witnessed the trial. My self-worth and confidence were lost. The memory of it still troubles me. (Divorcee 14, Age: 38)

Participant 15, a female divorcee, recounted her own experience:

The whole process felt like I was a bad wife and was tried for that reason, instead of me being made to feel like I was moving away from a toxic marriage, which was really the case. The process was not only emotionally abusive but also physically draining. Going to court all the time to listen to such negative vibes was not good. It is highly shameful, undermining, and undignified. (Divorcee 15, Age: 41)

Two family lawyers stated that the adversarial nature of the divorce process could be related to the extent to which the litigation is prolonged and the emotional trauma associated with it. In his narration, family lawyer 2 stated:

The integrity of people is normally at stake, and each party would like to defend his or her position. This can prolong the whole process for years since they don't want

to be associated with wrongdoing. To some divorcing parties, accepting a moral wrong has implications for their future relationship. (Family lawyer 2, Age: 36)

Another family lawyer, male participant 5, added:

Let me say that there are times the couples may have settled their issues, but immediately they begin to point out fault, it becomes difficult to address the matter. This is because pride takes over as each party wants to prove how important or superior they are. This creates a situation where no party wants to compromise, thereby prolonging the litigation. (Family lawyer 5, Age: 47)

These findings show that the burden of proving fault does not merely serve a legal function but actively intensifies conflict, deepens emotional injury, and delays closure for many litigants.

Away from the adversarial and emotional burden associated with the fault-based foundation of the Act, another theme that emerged is the gendered impact of fault-based divorce. The female divorcees and scholars revealed the unequal harm imposed by the fault-based system. The females generally explained the extent to which societal expectations of marriage and the role of women made it challenging to prove fault. Divorcee 16, female participant, stated that:

It appeared the court expected me to demonstrate that I was a good wife to my husband. It is as if the court would only grant me audience after I had proved that. I did not get that impression in the case of the man. (Divorcee 16, Age: 50)

Another female divorcee, participant 20, stated:

I feel sad about the whole process because even when it is obvious that the man is unfaithful, people seem interested in what the woman did for the man to engage in an extramarital affair. It is like the woman is the source of all marital problems. (Divorcee 20, Age: 45)

This position was further recounted by another divorcee, participant 30:

Are women the source of all marital problems? Why do people, including women, tend to think that the woman must have been the problem? The types of questions sometimes asked by judges and lawyers in court sometimes tend to suggest that we are the cause of the marital failure. What makes it worse is that at times the

men tend to flip the blame on us. This is pathetic. The reality is that this affects our being as women. (Divorcee 30, Age: 44)

Some of the family lawyers confirmed this position of placing the evidence and social burdens in fault-based cases on women. According to a family lawyer, female participant 11:

The men easily allege desertion, and it appears okay. However, when it is alleged by a woman that a man has been cruel towards her, she is asked to show evidence of hospital reports, bring witnesses to support such a claim, and also provide further evidence if available. The burden is much heavier on the women compared to the men. (Family lawyer 11, Age: 40)

In the words of a legal academic who revealed the inequality that is entrenched in proving fault in divorce cases, he stated:

Looking at it on face value, you will think that the proving of fault signifies equality of power between the spouses. But looking at it much closer reveals something otherwise. The legal system, as it is now, rather reproduces inequality. And this is because the evidential burden is heavier on women. This is the fact. Even in Ghanaian marriages, there is no actual equality. (Legal academic 8, Age: 46)

For some divorcees, they were still trapped in abusive marriages just because proving fault was a herculean task. Even with knowledge and behaviour evidence, it was difficult for them to prove fault. A divorcee, female participant said:

Though we were apart due to my ex-husband's cruel behaviour, initially, it was very difficult for me to leave the marriage, just because I could not prove cruelty in court. I was trapped in the marriage for 6 years until I was set free. I know a woman who had to withdraw her case from court because of her inability to prove any fault, and she is suffering in the marriage. (Divorcee 29, Age: 43)

Another female divorcee added:

I am a divorcee, and I know many women want to divorce but don't have the evidence. To the extent that some women are even planning evidence against their husbands, because it is difficult for women to easily

gather evidence against their husbands. This is really torturing many women. Many women are indeed trapped. (Divorcee 22, Age: 45)

These narratives also show how the fault-based divorce function in a gendered way. Instead of protecting people who are at risk, it rather reinforces or perpetuates socio-economic vulnerabilities.

Another theme that emerged from the data is practical barriers to accessing non-fault separation grounds. In theory, the Act provides non-fault grounds for divorce, but such bases were considered to be impractical in real life by the participants. Participants described the separation with consent for two years provided by the Act as susceptible to abuse, especially by spouses who do not intend to cooperate. During the interview, a family lawyer, participant 6, had this to say:

From my experience, some spouses deliberately withhold their consent as a form of bargaining tool. Forcing the other partner to agree to certain terms and conditions. This ground for divorce becomes useless when a party refuses consent. (Family Lawyer, 6, Age: 55)

Another family lawyer, male participant 5, added:

What is the relevance of such a ground when it becomes useless upon a party refusing to consent? This ground imposes a strain in some ways. (Family lawyer 5, Age: 47)

Described as unrealistic was the separation for five years without consent, especially for women and spouses who were independent economically. A female divorcee, participant 20, explained:

This ground is hilarious. If we separate without consent, why should someone wait for five years to be legally free from that marriage? Five years is such a long time. So, your life will be on hold during those five years. Just imagine what you can achieve during that period. The psychological burden is unacceptable. I think this ground really provides the space for people to engage in bad activities to facilitate the divorce. (Divorcee 20, Age: 45)

Female divorcee 22 stated:

For me, at the time, I knew I had emotionally moved on already. I was not dependent on the man, so why should I be held hostage by the law? It is funny that the law expected that I wait for five years. It is as though waiting for that period would heal everything. Waiting for that

period is what I would describe as the period of marital imprisonment and pain. (Divorcee 22, Age: 45)

Some family lawyers confirmed that, as a result of this long wait, which is more like an impediment, they advised some clients to plead fault even though there may not be any serious misconduct. Making his point, family lawyer 1 said:

It emerged that some of my clients were reluctant to accuse their spouse of any wrongdoing. But I told them that the only exit route for the easy dissolution of the marriage was to label and prove fault. ...it is obvious from the Act that fault is the only practical exit option. (Family lawyer 1, Age: 55)

Interviewing female family lawyer 11, she added that:

The grounds for separation seem good theoretically, but practically serve as barriers. It pushes people to make every effort to prove fault. I am tempted to believe that because of this, some spouses go to the extent of setting traps for their partner. There was a time a female spouse told me she was tempted to engage the services of a professional prostitute to entice her husband to bed so she could get good evidence. (Family lawyer 11, Age: 40)

From the narratives, it can be said that the structure of the matrimonial legal regime forces divorce seekers to depend on fault-based claims. This is so even in situations where both spouses agree to the dissolution of the marriage.

There seems to be strong support for a no-fault-based legal regime from divorcees, family lawyers, and legal academics. This support was premised on viewing Act 367 as socially injurious and dated. Female legal academic 10 stated:

In modern-day Ghana, marriage must be viewed as another form of partnership. It should not be a punishment. People must agree to disagree and separate at will. The law should be reviewed to reflect this reality. (Legal academic 10, Age: 45)

Male legal academic 11 looked at the constitutional dimension:

The implicit force perpetuated by the Act, by trapping people to be legally married just because it is difficult for them to prove fault in many ways, undermines personal autonomy or freedom, and the dignity of the people seeking divorce. (Legal academic 11, Age: 42)

The legal practitioners recommended the need for legal reform. Female family lawyer 2 noted:

The decision to remove fault from the law would imply the decision to reduce trauma and bitterness from the divorce process. It also reduces the level of accusations and the blame game. (Family lawyer 2, Age: 36)

Male family lawyer 1 added:

Moving away from fault-based to a no-fault-based based tends to reduce perjury since people would have no reason to falsely accuse their partners of misconduct with the intention of satisfying the law. The current law is draconian. (Family lawyer 1, Age: 55)

Apart from legal academics and lawyers asking for reform in the Matrimonial Act, divorcees expressed the same sentiments. Female divorcee 30 stated:

If I had my way, I would not have accused him of anything because I have children with him. I believe not accusing him of infidelity or blaming him for anything would have rather helped my healing process to be faster. There is nothing positive about trying to prove that he was the wrongdoer. In the instant, it sounds well, but after further reflection, you would realize that it was unnecessary. (Divorcee 30, Age: 44)

Male divorcee 15 remarked that:

I only wanted a peaceful divorce, but the requirement of the law turned the whole process into a war, and the court premises as a war zone. I strongly believe that a genuine no-fault basis would promote a peaceful atmosphere for divorce. It would also ensure that the parties would continue to accord themselves with respect, even after the divorce. (Divorcee 15, Age: 56)

Female divorcee 19 reiterated the point that:

The process of divorce should not impose a burden on any party seeking divorce. The law should be structured to promote the respect and dignity of people. Proving fault is not the way to go. Even traditionally, when you want to divorce, you inform your family to return the bride price. Upon the agreement of the two families, the marriage is deemed annulled. Even though sometimes it can be chaotic, the process does not prolong the pain,

unlike the Act. A no-fault basis is obviously the future.
(Divorcee 19, Age: 51)

The data from divorcees, lawyers, and legal academics call for reform. The current form of the law, as the empirical data shows, appears inconsistent with the present social realities and understanding of marriage and divorce in Ghana.

DISCUSSION

The analysed data, both doctrinal and empirical, support the argument that the operative provisions of the Act continue to require proof of misconduct in a matrimonial dispute, regardless of the courts' references to the irretrievable breakdown of marriage. Even though the Act adopts the principle that before divorce is granted, the marriage should have broken down beyond reconciliation (Atupare & Yin, 2024), the lived operations of the Act and its structure suggest that proving fault is the fulcrum within which divorce litigation revolves. The combined doctrinal and empirical findings strongly support the latter position. Consistent with previous studies, the empirical data not only confirms how the Act aligns with the character of the court in its interpretation and the social experience of divorcees, but also shows the challenges posed by the Act in the divorce litigation process (Trinder et al., 2017; Hernawan et al., 2025).

In the doctrinal analysis, it was revealed that the provision for irretrievable breakdown in the Matrimonial Act was not a standalone principle, as has also been established by Ellman (1996), Morris (1972), Kumekpor (1975), Archampong (2007), and Sam (2012). Rather, it functioned in relation to the grounds for divorce stated under section 2 (Atupare & Yin, 2024). These grounds, particularly the first three, are classically described as fault-based. The empirical finding is consistent with the doctrinal argument of fault-based. The divorcees, family lawyers, and legal academics forcefully made the point that for a marriage to be dissolved, the petitioner had a duty to prove fault against the respondent in court. And that proving fault was the only way the court would have a justifiable basis to grant a divorce. The empirical data also show that even when spouses jointly agree that the marriage has broken down beyond repair and they want it dissolved peacefully and quickly, the parties are still required to prove the breakdown through allegations of misconduct. Participants' admission that sometimes what they told the court differed from the actual causes of their marital failure reveals the true nature of the law as actively manufacturing fault instead of merely identifying it. This position is consistent with the doctrinal

concerns that the matrimonial law appears to emphasize the language of breakdown, yet its operating principle is blame-based. This finding is consistent with the works of Parkinson (2011) and Diduck and Kaganas (2012), who found that grounds such as adultery and unreasonable behaviour in divorce laws are fault-based, whether the overarching principle is irretrievable breakdown or not. The finding that parties are compelled to frame allegations of misconduct even though the marriage has already collapsed resonates with the works of Brinig & Allen (2000) and Ellman (1996), who also found that the fault-based divorce approach forced parties to conjecture evidence of wrongdoing.

Doctrinally, the Act's adversarial approach of evidential requirements and the burden of proof was confirmed by the interview data. From the empirical findings, the petitioner has the responsibility to prove any of the following: alleged adultery, unreasonableness, and desertion. In proving this, some participants said the structure of the Act converted the divorce proceedings into a moral and character contest. Some participants further shared that the whole divorce process in court was more like a public fight over one's private affairs. This shows how private affairs have been converted into public adjudication by the Act. These data are not poles apart from the argument that the persistence of fault is an integral part of the procedural dynamics of divorce disputes, and not just symbolic. The consequences thereof, such as emotional and psychological harm, and prolonged divorce litigation, are not secondary repercussions but rather the deductive outcomes of a legal architecture that is fault-driven. The finding that divorce proceedings have become a show of moral and character contest in open court, which promotes conflict between parties, mirrors the works of Weitzman (1985) and Mnookin & Kornhauser (1979), who found that fault hearings during divorce escalated conflict between spouses. The finding of emotional and psychological trauma as outcomes of attempting to prove fault also aligns with the work of Ernest (2003).

In terms of gendered impact, Act 367 is considered to be gender-neutral; however, the practical application of the Act places women in a disadvantaged position. Looking at the Act, there is an assumption of equal access to evidence and equality of power between spouses; however, the empirical finding reveals that in practice, such equality hardly exists. In most areas of Ghana, women normally lack the financial and economic power, documentary evidence, and socio-cultural authority to meet the standard of evidentiary burden. This finding echoes with the work of Bazaanah and Ngcobo (2024) and Dowuona-Hammond et al. (2020), who found that women are dependent economically, constrained socially, and face disadvantages in their efforts to access evidence. Aside from these, women are also stigmatized when they are

to publicly prove fault against men. This finding confirms the work of Amara (2024), Bazaanah and Ngcobo (2024), who found that the fault-based divorce process disadvantaged women. Given the legal threshold of proof, the data reveal that some women are trapped in abusive marriages. In effect, being denied access to justice. This finding brings into line the feminist perspective that the matrimonial legal system is inherently and structurally biased, as it rather reproduces and entrenches the already existing power relations established by the dominant patriarchal cultures (Thomas, 2021; Painter, 2015; Apatinga, 2019; Adjei, 2017).

The supposed two non-fault grounds, that is, separation for two years with consent and five years of separation without consent, as revealed by the doctrinal analysis, do not offer real alternatives, but rather incite legal cynicism and legal estrangement, wherein people doubt the law/legal institution and its functionality as a prerequisite in their divorce pursuits. The separation for two years requires the consent of the other partner, which can be withheld. The five-year period without consent imposes an unrealistic period of waiting, which causes emotional and psychological trauma. The empirical data reveal that these two supposed non-fault grounds do not functionally offer feasible pathways to divorce. The divorcees and family lawyers saw consent as a tool to control the divorce process instead of a way of cooperating with the other partner. The participants also considered the waiting period of five years to be too long a waiting time and not in sync with socio-economic realities, and does not support one's emotional well-being. This makes aspiring divorcees prefer to go on the fault-based tangent even in situations of mutual agreement for separation. This shows that the Act invariably compels people seeking divorce to establish fault in the marriage as the main route of practical exit. The finding of long waiting periods and their emotional consequences is consistent with the works of McCormack (2025), Parkinson (2011), and Mukono (2021), who found that the long waiting period was emotionally harmful and unrealistic in the modern-day socio-economic context, which forced participants to bypass it. The emotionally traumatizing process of divorce was also found to echo the works of Fischel-Wolovick (2018) and Latifah and Peristiano (2024). These findings confirm the concerns raised by sociological jurisprudence, which holds that when law no longer aligns with lived social conditions, it produces outcomes that frustrate rather than serve the people it governs.

The data from all the categories of participants revealed that the fault-based approach is out of touch with social realities (Pound, 1912; Tamanaha, 2020; Cotterrell, 2017; Mamonto, Putri, & Salsabila, 2025). The no-fault reform ideology was widely accepted by most of the legal

practitioners who were interviewed. The practitioners' narratives that blame-based divorce perpetuates perjury and bitterness highlight the challenges associated with the current legal framework. The accounts by divorcees and legal academics are not different from what the family lawyers said. They all called for reform towards a no-fault approach. This collective demand for reform is consistent with the desire for a less adversarial or confrontational, efficient, and more dignified way of dissolving a marriage. This collective reform aligns with Amara (2024), who made a similar call.

Collectively, the discussion has shown that the fault-based approach has become a major source of procedural unfairness, harm to society, and gender inequality.

CONCLUSION

This paper examined Ghana's Matrimonial Causes Act, 1971 (Act 367) as a fault-based law. It argued that, although courts may refer to the irretrievable breakup of marriage, the Act nonetheless requires proof of misbehaviour in a matrimonial dispute. The paper further contended that the evidence of wrongdoing does not align with the present-day societal realities associated with marriages in Ghana.

The doctrinal analysis revealed that the principle of marriage broken down beyond reconciliation under the Act is not self-sufficient, as it functioned in relation to the fault-based grounds of adultery, unreasonable behaviour, and desertion. Even the two-year separation-based ground is limited, as consent may be withheld by the other partner. The five-year period without consent was also seen to impose an unrealistic period of waiting time, which ends up causing emotional and psychological trauma. In effect, these separation-based grounds are ineffective in contemporary Ghanaian society. The empirical data also confirm that the functional operating principle of the Act remains fault-based. To the extent that spouses seeking divorce conjecture fault to navigate the divorce process. To this end, the Act, as applied by the courts, has engendered a legal ambiguity for unwittingly discouraging amicable resolution of divorce between parties. As important as the "black letter of the law" is to the courts, a dose of legal realism on the adverse impact of the prevailing fault-based ground will go a long way in remedying the unwarranted show of acrimonious divorces. Participants suggested the need for Ghana to move away from the fault-based approach to a no-fault-based approach.

Given this conclusion, the following recommendations are made:

1. Act 367 should be amended so that irretrievable breakdown becomes a complete and independent ground for divorce, without requiring proof of adultery, unreasonable behaviour, or desertion. A clear no-fault pathway would reduce trauma, eliminate the incentive to manufacture allegations, and allow spouses to exit failed marriages with dignity. Such reform would also bring the law in line with constitutional values of equality, autonomy, and human dignity expressed by participants across the study.

2. A reformed divorce regime should therefore be supported by an institutional framework that encourages cooperation rather than blame. This should include: clear procedural guidelines for a no-fault divorce process; strengthened access to mediation and counselling; gender-sensitive judicial training; and public education by relevant state bodies to promote understanding of a dignified, non-fault approach to marital dissolution.

Together, these measures would ensure that a revised Act 367 operates effectively in practice and responds to the lived experiences documented in this study.

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The data collected for this study are with the author and would be shared upon request only.

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